

A Study of Clinico-Demographic Profile and Outcome in Patients Presenting with Atraumatic Altered Mental Status to the Emergency Department of a Tertiary Care Hospital

Patel JC¹, Patel PP^{*2}, Shingala DH³, Jarwani BS⁴

¹3rd Year Resident, Emergency Medicine, SVPIMSR, Smt. NHLMMC, Ahmedabad, 380006, India

²Assistant Professor, Emergency Medicine, SVPIMSR, Smt. NHLMMC, Ahmedabad, 380006, India

³2nd Year Resident, Emergency Medicine, SVPIMSR, Smt. NHLMMC, Ahmedabad, 380006, India

⁴Head of the Department of Emergency Medicine, SVPIMSR, Smt. NHLMMC, Ahmedabad, 380006, India

Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Prakruti P. Patel

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Altered mental status is very common yet highly non-specific presentation of patients to the Emergency Medicine Department (EMD). Altered mental status is broad general term which includes disorders associated with mental dysfunction ranging from slight confusion to coma [1]. Acute presentation of altered mental status may be the presentation of a patient as a result of underlying disease conditions including structural, metabolic, vascular or other conditions [2-4] or may be a late manifestation due to hypoxia or hypo perfusion to the brain⁽⁵⁾. Patients generally present with very vague complains; so their diagnosis and treatment are highly challenging for Emergency Physicians.

Aim: To study the clinico-demographic profile and outcome of patients presenting with atraumatic altered mental status to ER of the tertiary care hospital.

Methodology: This is prospective observational study. Total 139 Patients, presenting with acute onset altered mental status and meets inclusion criteria were included and studied. GCS (Glasgow coma scale) was calculated on admission. Patients were managed according to standard treatment guidelines. Patient's outcome and length of hospital stay were recorded. All data was entered in Microsoft excel sheet and analysed in Epi info software version 7.2.6.0.

Results: Out of 139 patients of altered mental status, 91 (65.46%) were males and 48(34.53%) were females. The mean age of the patients with altered sensorium was 55.06±15.82 years. Maximum number of the patients was from 60 years and above age group, n=55 (39.56%). Ischemic stroke (20.14%) was most common aetiology among neurological causes followed by haemorrhagic stroke (13.66%), and hepatic encephalopathy (18.7%) was most common aetiology among metabolic causes followed by uremic encephalopathy(17.26%). Mortality rate and length of hospital stay were inversely related to on admission GCS score.

Conclusion: Overall mortality rate was 21.58%. Early identification of aetiology and prompt management shows favourable outcome. GCS calculation can help to determine prognosis of patients presenting with altered mental status to the Emergency Room.

Keywords: Altered Mental Status, Atraumatic, Glasgow Coma Scale, Emergency Department.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Altered mental status is very common yet highly non-specific presentation of patients to the emergency department with studies reporting 4-10% of patients in ED diagnosed with it. Altered mental status is broad general term which includes disorders associated with mental dysfunction ranging from slight confusion to coma [1]. Acute presentation of altered mental status can result from various underlying disease conditions, such as structural, metabolic, vascular, or other conditions [2-4]. It may also be a late manifestation due to

hypoxia or hypo perfusion to the brain [5]. Additionally, altered mental status can be the first symptom of a more serious condition like a cerebrovascular event or be a component of a diagnosis like dementia [6]. Aetiologies of Altered mental status can range from primary CNS disorders to secondary processes with an effect on CNS. On the basis of duration, AMS is divided in acute, sub-acute, and chronic, i.e., processes of <24 hours, those of <1 week duration, and those of >1 week duration. AMS is a common symptom

complex that carries a significant length of hospital stay and mortality [1]. It is important to manage patients with acute mental status changes with proper allocation of resources from triaging to investigation and management in the emergency department (ED). Since the aetiologies of altered mental status can vary geographically, understanding the common causes and available diagnostic tools will aid emergency physicians in the effective management of these patients. GCS

(Glasgow coma scale) is very important scale which is calculated by easily identifiable behavioural features. It has three components: Eye opening, verbal response and motor response. Maximum GCS score can be 15 and minimum can be 3. Patients can be classified based on GCS into three categories; Severe (GCS <8), moderate (9-13), mild (14-15). GCS can be used as a bedside tool for triaging the altered mental status patients.

Table 1: GCS (Glasgow coma scale)

Eye opening	Verbal response	Motor response
4 - spontaneous	5 - oriented	6 - obeys command
3 - to verbal command	4 - confused	5 - localises pain
2 - to pain	3- inappropriate words	4 - withdrawal from pain
1- no eye opening	2 - incomprehensible sounds	3 - abnormal flexion
	1 - no verbal response	2 - abnormal extension
		1 - no motor response

Aim: To study the clinico-demographic profile and outcome of patients presenting with atraumatic altered mental status to ED of the tertiary care hospital.

Objectives:

- To assess clinical profile (sign and symptoms) and demographic profile among patients presenting with altered mental status to ED.
- To evaluate the aetiology of altered mental status patients presenting to ED of the tertiary care hospital.
- To determine mortality and length of stay by using on admission GCS score in patients presenting with altered mental status in ED.

Material and Methodology:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patient above 18 years of age.
- Patient with altered mental status

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients below 18 years of age.
- Patient's relatives not willing to be included in the study.

Methods:

This is prospective observational study with the sample size of 135. Total 139 Patients, presenting

with acute onset altered mental status and meets inclusion criteria were included and studied. Written informed consent was taken from patient's relatives. Detailed medical and neurological examination was done in each patient at time of presentation. All routine blood (CBC, RFT, LFT, Coagulation profile, ABG analysis, s. ammonia, RBS, procalcitonin) and radiological investigations [Chest x-ray, USG abdomen, CT brain and MRI brain (when required)] were obtained. CSF analysis was obtained in suspected CNS infections. GCS (Glasgow coma scale) was calculated on admission in all patients. Patients were managed according to standard treatment guidelines. Patient's outcome and length of hospital stay were recorded.

Statistical Analysis: All data was entered in Microsoft excel sheet and analysed in Epi info software version 7.2.6.0. Descriptive statistics for continuous variables like mean as a measure of central tendency and standard deviation as a measure of dispersion were determined. For categorical variables percentage and frequency were obtained. To represent data appropriate graphical tools were used. $p < 0.05$ is statistically significant.

Results:

A total of 139 patients who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled and studied.

Table 2: Age and gender distribution of altered sensorium patients (n=139)

Age group	Male	Female	Total
18-30	4	5	9
31-40	16	3	19
41-50	19	6	25
51-60	18	13	31
61 and above	34	21	55
	91 (65.46%)	48(34.53%)	139

Figure 1: signs and symptoms in patients with altered mental status

Table 3: etiological distribution of patients with altered sensorium

	Diagnosis	Patients
Neurological causes	Ischemic stroke	28
	Haemorrhagic stroke	19
	CNS infections	16
	SOL	1
	Status epilepticus	3
Non-neurological causes	Metabolic encephalopathy	68
	Hypertensive encephalopathy	1
	Toxins/Drugs	2
	Hypoxia	1
Total		139

Table 4: GCS on admission and its relation with Outcome (mortality)

GCS	Death		Survived		Total no of patients
	Neurological causes	Non-neurological causes	Neurological causes	Non-neurological causes	
< 8	9	1	9	11	30(21.58%)
9-13	1	15	26	30	72(51.79%)
14-15	1	3	21	8	37(26.61%)
	30(21.58%)		109(78.41%)		139

p=0.00026

Table 5: GCS on admission and its relation with average length of stay

GCS	Average length of stay (In days)		
	Neurological causes	Non-neurological causes	Overall
<8	7.94	11.25	9.26
9-13	7.42	6.0	6.55
14-15	5.59	5.13	5.40

$r=-0.219, p=0.009$

Discussion

In our study, 139 patients with altered mental status were studied based on aetiology and clinical signs and symptoms. Age of patients range from 19 to 91 with mean age of 55.06 ± 15.82 . Among them 91 (65.46%) patients was Male with mean age of 53.91 ± 15.35 years and 48 (34.53%) were Females with mean age 57.25 ± 16.62 years and male to female ratio of 1.89:1. Age group of 60 years and above comprises of maximum number of patients, $n=55$ (39.56%) followed by the age group of 51 to 60 years, $n=31$ (22.3%). In a study done by Cherukuri et al. mean age was 52.3 ± 17.84 with male patients being 62.4% [7]. In this study, apart from altered mental status the most common symptom was fever, which was present in 59 (42.44%) patients, followed by limb weakness which was present in 38 (27.33%) patients. Hypertension was the most common risk factor ($n=72$) followed by diabetes mellitus ($n=54$). Altered mental status aetiologies can be divided broadly into two categories: Neurological and non-neurological.

In our study, Among 139 cases, 67 (48.2%) patients were diagnosed with neurological causes and 72 (51.8%) patients had non-neurological causes. Among neurological causes, ischemic stroke was most common cause, $n=28$ (20.14%), followed by haemorrhagic stroke, $n=19$ (13.66%). Among non-neurological causes metabolic encephalopathy was most common causes, $n=68$ (which comprises uremic encephalopathy, hepatic encephalopathy, septic encephalopathy, hyponatremia, hypoglycaemic encephalopathy, diabetic ketoacidosis). Hepatic encephalopathy was most common among metabolic causes, $n=26$ (18.7%) followed by uremic encephalopathy, $n=24$ (17.26%). In a study done by Kanich et al. neurological cases were 28% [8] and in another study done by Cherukuri et al. neurological cases were 37% [7].

In our study 21.5% mortality was observed. Out of 139 patients, 30 patients were presented with GCS <8, out of which 10 (33.33%) patients expired. 72 patients presented with GCS 9-13, out of which 16 (22.2%) patients expired, while out of 37 patients presented with GCS 14-15, 4 (10.8%) patients expired. Mean GCS of survived patients was 11.41 ± 2.72 , and of dead patients was 9.36 ± 3.63 with $p=0.00026$. It suggests lower GCS

has higher mortality. In a study done by Cherukuri et al, 11.5% mortality was observed [7]. Higher mortality was observed in a study done by Kekec et al. which was 20.1% [9]. In our study, mean length of stay was 6.83 ± 5.49 days. Average length of stay in patients with GCS <8 was 9 days, while in patients with GCS >8, it was around 6.5 days. Higher mortality rate and higher length of stay was observed in patients with low GCS. Applied correction between GCS and length of stay, $r = -0.219, p = 0.009$. It suggests decrease in GCS score has longer duration of stay.

Conclusion

Overall mortality rate was 21.58%. Early identification of aetiology and prompt management shows favourable outcome. GCS calculation can help to determine prognosis of patients presenting with altered mental status to the Emergency Room. Mortality rate and length of hospital stay were inversely related to on admission GCS score.

Limitation: Single centred study, Sample size is small. Many other factors can affect mortality in altered sensorium patient other than underlying cause.

Ethical statement: Ethical permission was received from the institutional review board Smt.NHLMCC, Ahmadabad, Gujarat.

List of abbreviation: ABG: Arterial blood gas, AMS: Altered mental status, CBC: Complete blood count, CNS: Central nervous system, CSF: Cerebrospinal fluid, CT: Computed tomography, ED: Emergency Department, EMD: Emergency Medicine Department, GCS: Glasgow coma scale, LFT: Liver function test, MRI: magnetic resonance imaging, RBS: Random blood sugar, RFT: Renal function test, USG: Ultra sonography

Data availability: Excel sheet with all data will be available with the correspond author.

Authors' contributions:

Dr Jaydip Patel, Dr. Prakruti Patel and Dr. Darshan Shingala has contributed to the conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, resources and writing (original draft). Dr Bhavesh Jarwani has contributed to supervision, validation, and writing (review and editing). All the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

References

1. Wilber ST. Altered mental status in older emergency department patients. *Emerg Med Clin North Am.* 2006 May; 24(2):299–316. vi. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
2. Tiffany M, Osborn M. Mental status is a predictor of mortality in CAP. *NEJM Journal Watch.* 2006.
3. Kataja A, Tarvasmäki T, Lassus J, Køber L, Sionis A, Spinar J, et al. Altered mental status predicts mortality in cardiogenic shock—results from the CardShock study. *Eur Heart J Acute Cardiovasc Care.* 2018 Feb 1; 7(1):38–44. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
4. Saedian J, Prahlow J. Hypothermia deaths and altered mental status. *Research Day.* 2019.
5. Tyson B, Erdodi L, Ray S, Agarwal P. Altered mental status in 71 deaths due to COVID-19. *Int J Neurosci.* 2020 Oct 1; 1–4. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
6. Wilber ST, Ondrejka JE. Altered mental status and delirium. *Emerg Med Clin North Am.* 2016 Aug; 34(3):649–65. [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
7. Cherukuri, Sai Kiran; Dhanawade, Vineet Subodh. Altered Mental Status in the Emergency Department, a Retrospective Analysis. *Current Medical Issues* 18(4):p 300-304, Oct–Dec 2020. | DOI: 10.4103/cmi.cmi_64_20
8. Kanich W, Brady WJ, Huff JS, Perron AD, Holstege C, Lindbeck G, et al Altered mental status: Evaluation and etiology in the ED *Am J Emerg Med.* 2002;20:613–7
9. Kekec Z, Senol V, Koc F, Seydaoglu G. Analysis of altered mental status in Turkey *Int J Neurosci.* 2008; 118:609–17.